

The Power of Healing: Decolonizing Feminist Reading of Luke 9:49-50 and the Traditional Healers in the Philippines

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Abstract

The Philippines has a long custom of traditional healers passed down through the generations since time immemorial. Upon the Emergence of top-notch medical schools - producing doctors and nurses around the world, the traditional healing continued to thrive amongst the population in far-flung islands and barrios in the country. On the other hand, in the public square of theology, they remained “silenced” and “unheard” towards agent of “Christ Healing.” This study explored the postcolonial reading of the traditional healers in the Philippines. It sketched the history of Traditional Healers in the Philippines from ancient to present. This quest reinforced deeper analysis through “in - depth individual interview” with 3 traditional healers (Case Study based). Furthermore, this paper exposed the present reception of the Catholic Church on “Traditional Healers.” Ultimately, this paper decolonized a feminist reading through the Gospel of Luke 9: 49 - 50.

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Introduction

The existence of traditional healing dates back from 14,000 centuries B.C., until Chinese, Graeco-Arabic and western countries using traditional medicines. It is the oldest form of structured healing, which is practiced with basic set of tenets (Medicine Network, 2003). Before modern medicines have been introduced in the Philippines, our early ancestors have engaged in traditional healing. According to Del Fierro and Nolasco (2013), a local healer is a local medicinal doctor who resorts to indigenous means of treating patients who are in pain or have long been suffering from various forms of illness caused by supernatural factors.

But as time passes by, that kind of practice is already slowly diminishing, brought by modernity and inventions in medicine. People rely more on professional medical practitioners who use science or modern medicine to cure diseases. Despite the extensiveness, power, and capacity of modern medical science, large portion of our human population can never avail its benefits, because of their impoverished economic situation. At the turn of the century, traditional medicine is practiced among the poor communities in rural villages. The healthcare needs of the Philippines is associated to power and capacity, because only the rich can avail of the modern hospital facilities, while the poor is part of an estimated 50%, who rely on the use of folk healing (Gilani, 2005).

Women are emerging in all aspects of society to bring healing, enlightenment, education, change, and spirituality to the evolution of humanity. They are highly respected because of their craft in folk healing, which is learned through observation, imitation and experience (Thomas, 2003).

This paper aims for a postcolonial reading of traditional women healers against the backdrop of Luke 9:49-50. Specifically, the paper seeks to answer the following: What does the literature say about traditional healing in the Philippines? How do the traditional healers cure the sick? What are the similarities and differences between biblical healing and traditional healing? How do they enrich and critique each other? What is the significance of the chapter 9 of the Gospel of Luke in shaping our attitude toward traditional healers today?

Methodology

The paper used the descriptive method through hermeneutical and deconstruction approach within the area of Ethnographic case study. Also, Decolonizing Feminist reading is fused in this research to unleash an authentic reading of Feminism (Dube, 2006). Common themes on the testimonies of the local healers are used for a reference of discussion. Their stories served as an avenue to dig deeper into the origin of the traditional healing in the Philippines. Add to this, it shall be supplemented of review of related literature on the study of local healers and Babaylans. It shall expose how the Spanish colonization dealt with the Babaylans during Spanish occupation. Ultimately, it attempts to present the power of women's healing in Jesus' spirit as presented in the Gospel episode of Luke 9:49-50.

Review of Related Literature

Folk healing in the present situation of the Philippines was quite similar to what the early Filipinos did. The descriptions of the early Spanish chroniclers (such as Aduarter, Chirino, Colin, Loarca, Placencia) on the early healers are similar to present-day situations (Blair and Robertson, 1976). The Spanish chroniclers called them baylan, babaylan, catalonan, etc., and associated their practices with the devil. The word "devil" is supported by the study of Mangahas (2010). Mangahas (2010) borrows the word of Antonio Pigafeta, 'when Spaniard came in 16th century, Spaniard changed the name into bruja.' A study of Magos (1992) states that even the historian Antonio de Morga would assert that Spaniard called them 'deceits who invoked the evil spirits through rituals and prayers.' Babaylans, (also balians or katalonans, among many other names), were animistic shamans of the various ethnic groups of the pre-colonial Philippine islands (Cole and Gale, 1922). These shamans were women or feminized men (asogor bayok). They were believed to have spirit guides, by which they could contact and interact with the spirits (anito) and the spirit world. In most Philippine ethnic groups, shamans were predominantly female due to the role of the shaman (especially the medium) being an intrinsically feminine one (Brewer, 1999). Mercado (1988) explained that traditional healers mediate with the spirits through ecstatic (e.g. trance, dreams and traditional). Mercado pointed that in the process of healing, the spirits appeared to them in order to give the antidote (e.g. sacred objects and sacrifices). Hence, their primary roles were mediums during pag-anito séance rituals. There were also various subtypes of Babaylan specializing in the arts of healing and herbalism, divination, and sorcery (Scott, 1992). The Babaylans were highly respected members of the community, on par with the pre-colonial noble class (Scott, 1994, Mallari, 2013, McCoy, 1982). Dagmang (1994) explained that in pre-Hispanic times religion was healing and healing was a religious ceremony that the folks usually hold in places called "simbahan" their place of worship. In all these healing rituals ("*mag-aanito*" or "*magdidiwata*") there was this babaylan who, used herbs and other indigenous materials and called on the anitoto take away sickness.

Basic to this practice of propitiation is the underlying belief informing it—that everything that happens in this world is attributable to an anito of some kind. Benevolent and malevolent ones roam around our world. In all that happens, good or bad, we are supposed to call on these anitos to render to them gratitude for the benefits they shower on us or to plead for mercy or exemption from suffering in case of sickness and other misfortunes.

One study claims that the modern Filipino faith healers are the continuation, and development, of a Filipino "pre-Hispanic medico-religious system of beliefs and practices" (Salazar, 1980). But, for the modern Filipino healers, the spirits, calling the shamans, have Christian names. Thus, Eleuterio Terte, the first notable Filipino psychic surgeon, got his call in 1925, when two angelic children appeared to him, when he was seriously ill. He was promised a cure if he would accept the mission to heal others (Licauco, 1982). Jun Labo, another famous healer, based in Baguio, claims he received his calling when Jesus Christ appeared to him (Licauco, 1982). Mari Daylo, a healer from Leyte, was promised a cure from her ailment by the apparition, in a dream, of St Michael, the Archangel, and she, in turn, promised to heal other people (Tiston, 1985). If one will look in the movement, there is a gradual integration of Christian faith. Swann (1997) coined this as "Identity Negotiation." Swann was concerned with the processes that affected changes to personal identity. His terminology and a similar concept of 'negotiation' is a socially located process of identity construction. Hence, it has been appropriated and further developed by identity theorists interested in issues of political, religion and cultural representation.

The shaman's training is the learning of "secret language" and "animal language" (Eliade, 1970). The Filipino folk-healers have to memorize plenty of pig Latin prayers and formulae, which they think will affect the cure. Jocano (1981) has documented the pig Latin prayers used by the healers around the Laguna de Bay area. The popular healer, Alex Orbito, has a mantra, which he prays in healing (Licauco, 1982).

Old and New healers identified two classification of diseases: those that are naturally-caused, and those that are supernaturally-caused (Salazar, 1980). Naturally-caused diseases need medicine, like herbs, and the like. In the modern context, they need the help of the doctor. However, supernaturally-caused diseases, such as those caused by witchcraft, cannot be cured by doctors, but by arbularyos, or shamans. Whereas, the Filipino shamans, long ago, were mostly female, the present healers are mostly male and do their healing in a clinical setting.

However, at present, there are individuals who are tough ones with the existent of traditional healers. One for instance, a lay speaker strongly discouraged more than a thousand singles present at a recent CFC (Singles for Christ Metro Manila Regional Conference workshop) from going to albularyos or faith healers, saying sick people should receive the healing sacraments of the Church instead (CBCP News, Ditch Albularyos, get real healing, 2015).

The lay leader added, “never ever go to albularyos. Go to the church and receive the sacrament of the anointing of the sick. That is the real sacrament of healing,” said Phil De Guzman, a lay volunteer of the Archdiocese of Manila’s Office of Exorcism under chief exorcist Fr. Jocis Syquia. In an exclusive interview with CBCP News, he (De Guzman) explained the faith healer’s so-called prayer incantations are not real prayers, as far as the Catholic faith is concerned. “[The part] where they pray, you call that an incantation. It’s not real prayer... It’s only magical... because the real prayer comes from the heart,” De Guzman explained further in Filipino, noting that even the sacramentals the faith healers bring with them, such as religious images, rosaries, or medallions, are not blessed (CBCP News, Ditch Albularyo, get real healing, 2015).

Case and Findings of the Study

Healer 1: She is Sofing (Not her real name). Married and blessed with seven (7) children and her husband is a tricycle driver. She is a local healer for the past 25 years. She is 65 years old.

Healer 2: Yna is her name (Not the real name). Married and have three children. She is 63 years old. She was a catechist of her former parish before she transferred to her current address. She is into healing activities for 18 years.

Healer 3: Nida (Not her real name). Like Sofing and Yna, she is married with four children. Her husband is a farmer and her assistant during healing activities. She is 70 years old and into healing for 23 years.

The Power of Prayers

The local healers make use of prayers, specifically identified as *orasyon* in treating whatever ailments or diseases. Often, *orasyon* is written in Latin, which is known to be the language of God. Two of the respondents reveal that they use “*librito*”, a book composed of several *orasyon* (e.g., Divine Mercy Prayer). H1 said that her *librito* is written in several languages with 73 prayers and 21 of those are Latin *orasyon*. Although not all of them have *librito*, it does not lead to the absence of *orasyon* (especially the power of calling the name of Jesus in the ritual), in every healing procedure that they perform.

H2 acquires her ability to utter *orasyon* from her unusual trainings in her dream of which she testified that prayers should be done to make her healing craft effective. “*Pinag- orasyon ko siya para gumaling siya dahil siya ay nabinat*” (I let her say a prayer because it alleviates his or her suffering of fatigue), She answered when asked of the reason of uttering prayers to one of her patients upon performing the healing process called “*tayhop*” (gentle blowing). The remaining two *manggagamot* are also asked on the necessity of the said *orasyon*. Their responses suggest that an *orasyon* is neither a healing guide nor a source of healing abilities.

Despite all the uncertainties, it is undeniable that traditional healing is strongly driven and influenced by the Christian faith similarly to other traditional healing practices in the Philippines. This is Traditional belief that prayer and faith blend together for efficient healing.

The Origin of the Gift of Healing

Most of the *manggagamot* claim that their healing abilities originated from their ancestors and were passed on through the next generation. While some confessed that they obtained their healing abilities through apparition. Two of them said that their calling begun through a series of apparition. H2 laments “*Siguro ito ay ipinagkaloob sa akin ng Diyos.*” (Yes, maybe it’s the will of God that He bestowed me the ability to heal). When asked how her calling begun, she answered, “*Minsan nananaginip ako nananggagamot ako, may nakikita akong isang matandang babae na may binubulong sa akin at sinasabi sa akin kong paanu gamitin.*” (There are times that I am dreaming of an elderly, giving me words on how it will be done, then with that, I knew I can). If some *manggagamot* attained their healing abilities through apparition, there were some of them who attained healing abilities to heal from their ancestors and passed on through the next generation.

In every interview, *manggagamot* has their own story in acquiring their healing abilities. Despite their differences, they all have the same goal—to heal the sick, since they believe that healing their patients is their mission to the community.

Traditional Healing as an Alternative

According to the respondents, the most suitable day for healing is every Friday and Tuesday. For them, their patients considered traditional healing as an alternative to medical practice because of financial constraint. H3 said, “*dito sa amin, sila ang kusang nagbibigay. Wala kami ng presyo na katulad sa hospital.*” (Here, our patients are given freely. We don’t demand any rate or charge). H2 added, “*mgatao sa probinsya sa amin ang punta dahil wala silang pera.*” (People at the province visited us for healing because they don’t have money).

Evidently, patients consult traditional healers instead of a professional doctor for medical help because they are not required to pay a fix amount unless they donate. Contrary to the hospitals or clinics where a consultation fee is required for every transaction made. This is supported by the study of Dr. Vergie Bonocan Maquiabas, that the age-old practices continue despite modern day science because those who seek it finds it cheaper and sometimes more effective than relying on medical experts (Cryer & Thomsen, 2001).

Limitation to financial resources affects choices and actions of people toward healing. In the state of impoverished situation, people may resort to inexpensive ways even if the ailment requires care of licensed physicians. This context mirrors the shades of poverty, where people cannot afford to avail the health services in medical centers, because they only give a little amount to the *manggagamot* for his or her rendered service, which is called *pahalipay* or an act of offering.

The majority of healers feel that their ministry is a gift, which must also be given freely. They also receive money, or reward (yet voluntary), for their sustenance, and the support of their families. But they also give away plenty of what they receive to charity. If the healer can detach himself from material success, he will not lose his power. Since the Philippine healers are also human, they may be subject to human frailty, like gambling, liquor, and extra-marital sex. But, as long as they do not allow these vices to dominate their personality, and as long as they keep healing as their main ministry, they will not lose their power. Otherwise, they cannot effect lasting cures (Licauco, 1982).

Healing as God's Grace

Healing power may be translated as *bisa*, *gahum*, or *pigsa*, respectively, in Cebuano Visayan, Tagalog, and Ilocano – the three most-widely-used Philippine languages. The healers describe the healing power differently. It may be a hard, ball-like substance inside the body of the healer, or a kind of force coming from the blood, or like an electric current, with paralysing strength, or a cold feeling, then becoming warm, coming from God (Jocano, 1973).

To the mind of respondents, the power of healing is both acquired, and a gift. To a certain degree, the powers of healing may be acquired through human effort. Arens reports that the shamans are directed towards the acquisition of power. Arens adds that the shamans in Biliran, an island near Leyte, have to spend nine Fridays in the sea, nine Fridays in the church, and nine days in the cemetery (Arens, 1982). But, concerning the higher forms of healing, this seems to be a God-given power. The healers also claim that their gift of healing comes from the spirits/saints, or from God. H1 shared, "Nagsisimba ako lagi. Galing kasi sa kanya ang aking gawaing ito." (I regularly attend mass. I believe what I have is from Him").

The testimonies of the healers are unanimous in saying that the positive disposition of the patient plays an important role in the healing process. Those who lack faith will make the cure harder and slower on the part of the healer. This means that no faith on the side of the patient will remain uncured. The healer's power can work, but often to a limited degree. H1 explained, "ang aking pangagamot ay walang say-say kong hindi naniniwala ang nagpapagamot na gagaling siya." (What I am doing is pointless if the patient doesn't believe that he/ she will be healed). H3 elaborated, "Sa pagpunta ng mga nagpapagamot dito sa akin, sila ay naniniwala na gagaling sila or kaya ko silang pagalingin sa gabay ni Sto. Nino." (Upon the decision of my patients in coming here, they believed that they will be healed in the name of Sto. Nino).

Since folk healing is greatly similar with Christian faith, most of the local healers utter prayers to the images of significant figures of the Christian religion like: Virgin Mary, the statues of the Señor Santo Nino, Image of the Divine Mercy, the Holy family, and the Crucified Christ, before performing a certain healing procedure to the patient (Gaabucayan, 2012).

Traditional healing is a part of Philippine society and culture. It is said that traditional healing practice is combined to Christian belief when Magellan has converted the Cebuanos (the people of Cebu) to Catholicism. A folk healer, according to Leiban is said to have an unusual connection with the spiritual world, which is derived from his or her mystical patron, in order to uphold the power to heal (Lieban, 1967).

Spiritual Discipline

Spiritual discipline is not to be understood here as the nuances of asceticism, which has stereotyped meanings in traditional Christian piety. This is maybe considered as a kind of discipline.

The explanation can be varied. One explanation is that the asceticism of the Filipino healer seems to be connected with the accumulation of power. All sacrifices – such as flagellation, or the use of amulets – are not for the forgiveness of sins, but to make the body acquire more power (Arens, 1982). The old shamans used to go to the caves for this purpose; on the other hand, the modern healers go to cemeteries. Their most-important season is Holy Week. Lent is said to be the season when the spirits give their power.

Prayers are the most carefully-guarded part of the healing technique, because they control the power of the healers. They serve as the link between the practitioner and the supernatural power, which, in the local concept, is actually responsible for the cure of an illness. The healer is merely a tool, through which the supernatural gift is given to the healer. Prayers are, thus, regarded as sacred symbols, that hold the key to an unseen source of power of "bisa" to overcome diseases (Jocano, 1973). On the other hand, the healers may be motivated by the Christian way for doing good. Most healers seem to be moved by this call, that since they have freely received the gift of healing, they must also freely give it away to others. Obedience to superiors is the test for spiritual discipline.

Women Healers and Luke 9:49-50

The foregoing phenomena of folk healing in the Philippines have parallels in the Bible specifically in the Gospels. Healing was essential to the ministry of Jesus. All four evangelists give examples of Jesus as a healer (Hill, 2007). In unconquered confidence, Jesus welcomed blind, crippled, leprous, even dead people into His presence. For Luke, this proleptic overview of Jesus' ministry is indicated in what Jesus read in Isaiah 61 1f., at the congregation of the synagogue of Nazareth:

The Spirit of the Lord is on me, because He has anointed me to preach good news to the poor. He has sent me to proclaim freedom for the prisoners and recovery of sight for the blind, to release the oppressed, to proclaim the year of the Lord's favor (Lk. 4.18.).

Luke also stresses that the ministry of healing (of which exorcism is a part), whether accomplished by Jesus himself (Luke 11.14-22) or by His disciples (Luke 10.17-19), is an attack on Satan's kingdom. 'Others' are also involved in the miracles of healing (Lk. 9.49f.), but Luke does not specifically use that pericope to underscore the defeat of Satan. Thus, Jesus thereby announced the arrival of the more powerful Kingdom of God through acts of healing by casting out demons.

As narrated in the Gospel episode of Luke, "And John answered and said, 'Master, we saw someone casting out demons in your name, and we forbade him because he does not follow with us.' And Jesus said to him, 'Do not forbid him, for he who is not against us is for us.'" (Luke 9:49-50).

Here's the kind of argument one might hear: "This man [sic] was not following Christ with Peter, James and John and the other apostles. He [sic] was working independent of 'Christ's group,' yet the Lord said: 'Do not forbid him[sic].' Hence, even though someone may not be with us; even if they happen to be in a denominational body, or teaching some things that are wrong; so long as they are not against us, and so long as they ascribe the name of Christ to their work, we should not forbid or criticize them (Brown et.,al, 1990).

Attention must be paid to what Jesus said about the person. One who wants to understand the text must carefully consider what Jesus said about this unnamed person. This unidentified "one", based on every indication of study, was a faithful disciple of Christ, though not in the literal company of the apostles. This teaches that those who are living and working in the name of Christ (by His authority) are not to be forbidden, even if they are unknown. He (Jesus) did not prohibit others from using His name in casting out demons, because – as He instructed His disciples – "anyone who is not against you is for you" (Luke 9:49-50). The power of healing, which the disciples, and early Christians, received was a gift from the Holy Spirit (Rom 12:9; 1 Cor 12:9; 28.30), and could not be bought (Acts 7:18-21).

R. B. Cherry (1999) views faith as a pathway of healing in which Jesus uses both the natural and the supernatural to heal, and calls anyone who believes in Him. Being healed has been described as a privilege of accepting Christ's redemption on the cross (Bosworth, 2001). As such, traditional healing is to be as a result of intercessory prayer to a saint or to a person with the gift of healing (Ascoli, 2009).

Thus, according to Graves (2011), healing is not primarily for the person healed, but for all people, as a sign of God's work in the ultimate healing called 'salvation', or a sign of the kingdom that is coming.

Conclusion

The present study demonstrated the situation of struggle of traditional healers for "authentic liberation." It was notable that in the history of traditional healers, women's held a high designation in society as "babaylans." In the dawn of colonization, they were demolished, demonized and branded as "witch" or "evil." Along the way, they learned to adopt and integrate in order to survive. Though they continue to survive, Babaylans continue to grapple with "authentic liberation" against the Patriarchal system (run by Catholic authority). Though, some of whom are sought after, they are given a special name – "pranic healers" which signify an "unauthentic healing." On the other hand, the reading of the Gospel of "Luke 9:49-50," invites for a postcolonial feminist reading. The narratives of Healer1, Healer2 and Healer 3 blend to the profound meaning of such Biblical text. They can be considered as "others" who continue to cure in the name of Jesus. Further, the unnamed person in the gospel episode is a representation of those who are fellow servants of Christ (9:49-50). This is exactly what Jesus did. He respected, valued and loved women - wanted to raise them up. One of the best places to see what Jesus thought of women, and how He treated them is the book of Luke. Of the four Gospels, Luke says the most about how Jesus interacted with women. There are more women in the Gospel of Luke than in any other Gospel (Brown, et.al., 1990). Ultimately, the church can only come up with postcolonial feminist reading of "traditional healers" if she crowd outs the illusion of the Patriarchal system – The priest and bishops (only men) – are capable of receiving the gift of healing, the power of Christ.

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